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WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract | A combined research design of a systematic literature review with semi-structured interviews is applied to understand material inputs and current and future trends in end-of-life treatment and foundation technologies on wind turbines. Material groups present correlations between materials used per component and rated power. A scenario for end-of-life treatment is built based on the interviews and literature. Natural conditions such as distance to shore and sea depth are deemed crucial for offshore foundations.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
DOI	Digital object identifier
EoL	End-of-life
CC	Climate change
CF	Characterization factor
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
ILCD	International Life Cycle Data
ReCiPe	RIVM and Radboud University, CML, and PRé
EF	Environmental footprint
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
GUI	Graphical user interface

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable aims to provide a state-of-the-art overview of the literature on life cycle assessment studies of wind turbines. Therefore, a systematic literature review is conducted. The literature review aims to identify studies publishing life cycle inventory data and determining, based on those, correlations between material masses and rated power. Additionally, semi-structured interviews are conducted with stakeholders involved in wind energy to understand existing and expected end-of-life treatments of wind turbines and foundation technologies for offshore installations. Together with WP2.5, a guideline for the interview is elaborated, and five interviews are conducted. Additionally, relevant studies are obtained from Elsevier ScienceDirect.

After reviewing 1,194 studies matching the search criteria, 30 studies were short-listed. The correlation between material use and rated power are presented in scatter plots with linear regression lines, and r^2 and p values are calculated to evaluate the statistical significance. Furthermore, the climate change impact of reviewed studies resulted in an average climate change impact of 18 gCO₂eq/kWh. Regarding end-of-life treatments, wind turbine blades pose the most significant challenge due to the utilization of composite materials. Chemical recycling of varied epoxy resins and adjusted solvents could solve this problem. Another current issue causing the limited growth of blade recycling is the delay in waste stream. When including offshore foundations, natural constraints, such as seabed ground and distance to the shore, are crucial for selecting the correct foundation type.

Finally, this deliverable serves as an input for the next deliverable D2.8. The material correlations are used to calculate the impacts of wind power combined with an existing Python package.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

All related task objectives are achieved.

1. INTRODUCTION

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a method to assess the environmental performance of products or services over their life cycle from raw material extraction through manufacturing, use and end-of-life (EoL) treatment. According to the international standards DIN ISO 14040 and 14041, LCA is divided into four phases: a) the goal and scope, b) the life cycle inventories, c) the life cycle impact assessment and d) the interpretation phase [1]. While goal and scope definition and the interpretation phase depend on the practitioner and the object of study, the life cycle inventory (LCI) assessment is a crucial part of each LCA [2]. The objective of this phase is to collect data, such as material, transport and processing information required over the product's life cycle. As the datasets of available databases are presented per unit of material/resource/transport, a high level of detail is required for the LCI data. Reliable data sources are, for example, the bill of materials of a wind turbine and information on manufacturing and transport requirements. This generates a conflict of interest: While the data needed to conduct an LCA is high, manufacturers see their competitive advantage at risk when providing such detailed LCI data, as it could reveal sensitive information, resulting in losing their competitive advantage. This also applies to the wind turbine industry: Providing sensitive LCI data containing specific information on material quantity and energy requirements at a component level might be revealing of the component design, e.g., the amount of glass fibre and epoxy resin used to manufacture a blade. Given this circumstance, realistic and timely LCA of new developments and products are scarcely available and difficult to obtain, or LCI data of published environmental impacts are aggregated. Thus, this poses a challenge to validate reported environmental impacts and use LCI data of new technologies for further exploration.

With an average carbon footprint over a 100-year time horizon of 14.2 gCO₂eq/kWh of wind-generated electricity in Europe in 2020 compared to 128 gCO₂eq/kWh electricity generated by natural gas power plants with carbon capture and storage, wind turbines have been identified as one possibility to reduce the GHG emissions in energy systems [3]. Therefore, considerable research has been conducted on the LCA of wind turbines, considering different technologies, locations, approaches, and scales. Besides academia, LCA is nowadays also requested by the authorities in public tenders for new wind farms. Recently, technological advancements in component reliability increased wind turbine sizes to surpass 10 MW

installed capacity. In 2023, Vestas installed the highest wind turbine in Europe, the V236-15.0 MW model [4]. At the same time, innovations are not only limited to the tower itself: larger wind turbines, especially for offshore turbines at deep water depth, call for alternative foundation solutions apart from mono-pile foundations, such as barge, spar-buoy, semi-submersible platform, tension-leg platform or others. Besides, wind turbines are considered an emerging technology with a worldwide growth of 98 in the last 25 years from 7.5 GW to 733 GW [5]. Assuming an average lifetime of 20 years [6]–[8], the first wind turbines are expected to be retired in the following years. Thus, more wind turbines must be treated once they reach their EoL. However, the treatment process, especially for turbine blades, is currently facing both technological uncertainty on the future recycling process and economic uncertainty related to the monetary value of recycled blade materials.

On the other hand, datasets of wind turbines in commercial databases for environmental impacts focus only on the wind turbine construction up until 4.5 MW (based on ecoinvent 3.9.1 database) [9]. Thus, recent developments in the wind turbine industry are not properly reflected. Additionally, while wind turbine datasets have some scrap and waste exchanges, the EoL treatment, considering additional material and energy requirements, is omitted.

This report contributes to filling the gap in LCI datasets of different wind turbines. Therefore, a literature review is conducted to identify LCA studies of onshore and offshore wind turbines. Particular interest is put on studies containing LCI data. Those data are further analysed to determine correlations between installed capacity per material used in the turbine components. Additionally, reported impact categories of the identified studies, such as climate change, are analysed.

Consequently, those correlations will be used in the second deliverable, D2.8, to calculate the environmental impacts of different wind turbines. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews are used with experts in the wind turbine industry to provide an understanding of the current and future status of the EoL of wind turbines. This deliverable will conclude by presenting an outlook, including the following steps to compute the impact calculation model of the upcoming 12 months.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This deliverable focuses on a literature review to identify correlations between material and rated power, an overview of reviewed papers' results for climate change (CC), and findings on EoL treatment and foundations of the turbines. The applied research design is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research design for D2.7 and interrelation with D2.8.

2.1 Literature review

A systematic literature review is conducted to identify studies showing an LCA for wind turbines and including publicly available LCI data. Those LCI data are afterwards used to determine correlations between rated power and the material needed for each wind turbine component. Thus, the research question of this deliverable is to understand how much of a particular material is required to manufacture a specific component in relation to the wind turbine's rated power. As a first step, LCI data of LCA studies on wind turbines are collected and listed per component in relation to its rated power. After data is harmonized, it is visualized in a scatter plot and linear regression models are computed along with the R-squared value. More specifically, a mathematical relationship between the rated power, representing an explanatory variable, and the material masses, representing the dependent variable is established. Next to this model, two statistic metrics are calculated to assess the performance and significance of the regression model: the coefficient of determination (r^2) and the p value. For the coefficient of determination, the correlation coefficient, represented by the variable r value, describes the strength and direction of the

relationship between rated power and material mass. By squaring the r value, the r^2 value provides an indication of the proportion of variability dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable.

The p value is a metric to test hypothesis of linear regression. It calculates the probability of observing the calculated slope under the null hypothesis that the actual slope is zero. Thus, a low p value confirms the statistical significance of the linear relationship between the dependent and explanatory variables.

After defining the research question, the search terms and the databases are defined. The following search terms are applied:

- Primary search string: "wind"
- Secondary search string: "Life cycle thinking", "sustainability", "life cycle assessment", "LCA"

Only peer-reviewed, scientific articles are defined as relevant in this literature review, and thus, the targeted database is Elsevier's ScienceDirect. The literature screening is identified with a Python script based on the Python package 'pyscopus' ([10], [11]). It helps to search Elsevier's database for papers containing the abovementioned terms. For relevant identified studies, descriptive information, such as titles, digital object identifiers (DOIs), journals, abstracts, etc., are exported into a spreadsheet. A similar approach in a different context is followed in Bekirsky et al. (2022) [12].

The outcome of the initial search lists 1,194 unique papers. Next, two qualitative filtering processes are undertaken: first, papers are deemed relevant if their abstract relates to wind energy. This first filtering reduced the number of relevant studies to 182. In a second filtering process, only studies mainly focused on wind turbines are included, leaving out all studies that address, for example, an evaluation of a new national energy system based on higher wind energy penetration. Those studies are neglected as the likelihood of containing new primary LCI data of individual wind turbines is perceived as low. As a result, the number of relevant publications is reduced to 101. Out of those 101 studies, 30 studies are reviewed. Unfortunately, 12 studies are excluded as they do not contain detailed LCI data or LCI only on a turbine, but not at the component level. A list of all 18 reviewed papers is included in the appendix. The search and filtering process is described in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Results of the systematic literature review.

2.2 Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured, in-depth interviews are conducted to understand better the current and future EoL treatment of wind turbines and the currently utilized foundation technologies for offshore wind turbines. To this extent, stakeholders involved in or investigating the EoL treatment, the commissioning, or involvement in the wind energy ecosphere are contacted. Therefore, a guideline was developed in cooperation with WP2.5 and is dedicated to job creation related to wind turbines. The guideline is composed as follows:

1. Warm-Up
2. Involvement in wind energy deployment
3. Jobs (type/duration/temporal nature/location)
4. Onshore vs Offshore scale influences
5. Data on foundation and EoL treatment
6. Wrap-Up – Final Self-Reflection

The complete guideline is attached in the ANNEX. Five semi-structured interviews are conducted with four stakeholders from the industry or private sector and one stakeholder from a research institute. This interview aims to understand the current and future EoL treatment of wind turbines and

utilized foundation technologies. Due to the number of interviews, no quantitative evaluation of the interviews is undertaken. Instead, the main points of the interviews are summarized and presented qualitatively, including conclusions on the LCA of WIMBY.

3. RESULTS

In general, the research on LCA of wind turbines can be divided into different classifications:

- Some literature presents environmental impacts on a very high level of detailed LCI data of one wind turbine technology [7], [13]. Studies aim to reveal the environmental impacts of wind turbine fleets from a systemic perspective [14]–[16].
- Alternatively, some LCA studies are dedicated to particular parts of the wind turbine, e.g., understanding the impact of maintenance for offshore wind turbines [13], the impact of EoL treatment of the blades [17], or the impact of different generator types installed in the rotor [18].

Furthermore, more than 50% of the reviewed studies assess onshore installations. At the same time, the reviewed papers with a rated power larger or equal to 3 MW are all offshore wind turbines.

The following subchapters present correlations of material masses and the rated power per turbine component. First, material types are used as categorical variables and are categorized into the following groups: concrete, ferrous metals, non-ferrous metals, rare-earth elements, polymers and composite materials. In the case where only a small number of data is available (and thus, no correlation could be obtained), the data is not included in the report. Data is presented in scatter plots, and linear regression model fit is used to have regression lines. Additionally, two main statistic metrics are presented as described in section 2.1: the r^2 and p values.

3.1 Material correlations

3.1.1 Foundation

The foundations are mainly composed of ferrous metals and concrete. For onshore installations, a similar amount of data is available for ferrous metals and concrete. In terms of rated power, data on wind turbine foundations for up to 5 MW rated power is included (see Figure 3). While the correlation of the concrete and rated power is higher than for ferrous metals, the p value of the ferrous metals is lower, indicating statistical significance. Additionally, only steel is used as metal in the foundation of onshore installations, which differs from offshore foundations. While steel is still the metal with the most

data points in offshore foundations, other ferrous metals, such as cast iron or iron ore, are also used. However, the r^2 and p values for cast iron and iron ore indicate a perfect correlation due to only two data points with a low statistical significance. For steel, the p value of 0.058 indicates a marginal level of significance of the null hypothesis. At the same time, the r^2 value of 0.17 indicates that only 17% of the variability in the steel mass variable can be explained by variations of the rated power.

Interestingly, there is much data for ferrous metals used in offshore foundations, while there is minimal data for concrete used in offshore installation. Additionally, data indicate that only metals are used for higher-rated powers in offshore installations, e.g., above 5 MW (see Figure 3). The low amount of concrete presented in offshore foundations on the bottom left sub-chart originates from one paper and is independent of the wind turbine size [7].

Figure 3: Correlation between materials used in the foundation and the installed power (r^2 value = Coefficient of determination, p value = hypothesis testing in the context of linear regression).

3.1.1 Tower

Most data on materials used in the towers of wind turbines are for steel (Figure 4). Furthermore, the r^2 value of 0.69 for steel used in towers of offshore wind turbines implies that about 69% of the variability in the steel mass can be linked to variations in the rated power. This points out a strong and significant linear relationship between those two variables. Additionally, an extremely low p value of $8.8e-07$ further underlines the statistical significance of this relationship. This low p value is a strong advocate towards rejecting the null hypothesis that the true slope is zero. To summarize, the relationship is not due to random chance. Similarly, the r^2 value of steel used in towers of onshore turbines of 0.79 means that around 79% of the variability in the steel amount is related to variations in the rated power. This reveals a stronger linear relationship compared to offshore turbines. At the same time, the p value is low, proving a statistical significance of the observed relationship. The probability of getting such results purely by chance is low. This statistical observation applies also to non-ferrous metals and concrete of offshore installations. Only two data points for copper and aluminium are available for onshore installations, and none for concrete. More data on aluminium used in the towers is present for offshore installations, while hardly any data is available for other non-ferrous metals.

Additionally, in literature, data on concrete used in offshore wind turbines' foundations are encountered, particularly for installations with a rated power between 5 and 15 MW. There is no data for concrete used in onshore towers (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Correlation between materials used in the tower and the installed power (r^2 value = Coefficient of determination, p value = hypothesis testing in the context of linear regression).

3.1.1 Nacelle

The nacelle contains the yaw drive and motor, depending on the turbine size, different generators and gearbox, a break, and shafts. Literature data is divided into ferrous and non-ferrous metals, composite materials, and rare-earth metals (Figure 5). Like the previous sections, the material data for offshore data is found for larger wind turbine installations (5–15 MW) rather than for onshore installations (up to 5 MW). The main ferrous metal for onshore installations is steel; up to 2.5 MW, some cast iron is used. The r^2 value of steel used in the nacelle of onshore turbines of 0.74 means that around 74% of the variability in the steel mass can be explained by variations in the rated power. This proves a strong positive correlation between steel mass in the nacelle of onshore turbines and rated power. An extremely low p value of $5.1e-7$ underlines the statistical significance of this relationship. In offshore turbines, the r^2 values of steel used in the nacelle is 0.24 and points towards a weaker, positive correlation compared to onshore turbines, explaining only 24% of the variability in the steel amount. A low p value of $5.2e-6$ indicates statistical significance despite the weak correlation. For cast iron used in nacelles of onshore turbines, an r^2 value of 0.72 suggests a strong, positive correlation, which explains 72% of the variability in the cast iron mass. The p value indicates statistical significance of those relationships. The r^2 value of 0.5 for cast iron used in nacelles of offshore turbine lower compared to onshore, proving a moderate, positive correlation. The p value of 0.011 implies statistical significance of the relationship. Furthermore, no study reported the utilization of rare-earth metals in onshore turbines' nacelle. In general, much more data is found for material utilization in the nacelles of offshore installations compared to onshore installations.

One study also reported the utilisation of ferrosilicon in the offshore nacelle, but the correlation is low, and statistically insignificant. More interesting is that the data of composite materials, glass fibre and epoxy resins used in the nacelle do not indicate strong correlations. The r^2 values for glass fibres and epoxy resins are 0.00 and 0.32. Additionally, from 5 MW onwards, rare earth metals are used in the nacelles of offshore turbines. Moreover, the utilization of rare-earth metals in the nacelle observed in offshore turbines from 5 to 15 MW onwards could be linked to a different drive technology used in the wind turbine generator. Unfortunately, the correlation between rare-earth metals and rated power is not very strong, and the p value is 0.52 (see Figure 5). To conclude, the materials used in the offshore nacelle show a greater variety compared to onshore installations. One reason for this could

be to increase the resistance of the nacelle to more extreme weather conditions in offshore areas and the associated complexity of the design of the nacelle.

Figure 5: Correlation between materials used in the nacelle and the installed power (r^2 value = Coefficient of determination, p value = hypothesis testing in the context of linear regression).

3.1.2 Rotor

The main part of the rotors are the blades. Those are mostly built of ferrous metals and composite materials (Figure 6). Furthermore, aluminium is also used for three offshore rotors, supported by a high correlation and statistical significant [19]. The ferrous metals included in the rotor are mainly cast iron and steel. For ferrous metals used in onshore and offshore turbines, there is a strong and linear relationship between the two metals and the rated power. Specifically for steel used in onshore rotors, the correlation coefficient is 0.40, pointing out a moderate, positive, linear relationship, while for steel used in offshore rotors a stronger, linear relationship is observed with a r^2 value of 0.64. On the other hand, for cast iron used in onshore turbines, an extremely high r^2 value of 0.99 indicates an almost perfect, positive, linear relationship. Similarly to onshore, cast iron used in offshore rotors show with an r^2 value of 0.98 a solid, linear relationship. For the offshore rotor, cast iron and steel utilisation is balanced for all rated power, while for onshore installations from 2.5 MW onwards, only cast iron is utilized [20].

The composite materials used in offshore installations are glass fibre and epoxy resins, with a strong correlation and a high statistical significance. For onshore installations, more data are available for glass fibres with a strong correlation of 0.81. Less data is available for epoxy resins in the onshore rotors, resulting in a weak correlation of 0.02 and a p value of 0.84. For onshore installations, most materials used in the rotor are around 2.5 MW, with a maximum of 5 MW installation (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Correlation between materials used in the rotor and the installed power (r^2 value = Coefficient of determination, p value = hypothesis testing in the context of linear regression).

3.2 Environmental impacts of different wind turbines

3.2.1 Climate change

This section presents the CC scores of all reviewed LCA studies. All studies are conducted from a cradle-to-grave approach. All CC impacts are shown per kWh in Figure 7 and no further harmonization is undertaken.

Generally, the average CC impact of all studies is 15.4 gCO₂eq/kWh with a minimum of 1.2 and a maximum of 116.3 gCO₂eq/kWh. To identify CC without taking into account outliers, those are removed for the following analysis and not included in Figure 7. As shown in Figure 7, offshore installations end up with either higher or lower greenhouse gas emissions per kWh compared to onshore, ranging from 1.2 to 18.6 gCO₂eq/kWh. The majority of offshore installations are equal or below 5 gCO₂eq/kWh, being considerably lower than onshore installations. Also at larger stage, the CC of offshore turbines remain below the onshore turbines. One reason could be that due to higher-rated power and thus a higher lifetime of electricity, the overall impacts of offshore installations are lower. Similar trends are also found in literature [22]. For offshore wind turbines, an average CC of 2.0 gCO₂eq/kWh is computed, while for onshore installations the average CC is 9.7 gCO₂eq/kWh, considerably above that of offshore installations. CC of onshore installations spread less than offshore installations, namely a minimum of 5.3 and a maximum of 18.8 gCO₂eq/kWh. Another point to mention is the functional unit: CC impacts are presented per generated kWh, which considers each turbine's location-specific energy production. If CC impacts would be presented per kW of rated power, neglecting their production, the impacts per turbine might be different.

Furthermore, studies report the CC impacts of wind turbines without specifying the type of turbine. The average CC of those studies is 16.5 gCO₂eq/kWh, the highest greenhouse gas emissions range from 6.0 to 28.6 gCO₂eq/kWh.

Figure 7 shows that the CC of offshore installations is somehow divided into low CC observed for turbines with a rated power until 5 MW. Furthermore, there are some turbines with slightly higher CC, but still well in the view of onshore turbines. Onshore installations seem to be more compressed in the area below 2.5 MW and higher CC can be observed for onshore installations. The highest CC are presented for turbines not indicating their type.

Figure 7: Climate change impact of reviewed wind turbine studies (n.a. = turbine type not specified).

3.2.1 Other impacts

CML is the most frequently applied life cycle impact assessment method, followed by ILCD, ReCiPe, EF3.0 and IPCC. Following Figure 8, CC is by far the most frequently assessed impact category (18 times), followed by ozone depletion (7 times) and terrestrial acidification (7 times). All impact categories chosen are on the midpoint level; no endpoint impact category is included. An overview of the frequency of reported impact categories is provided in Figure 8. Contradicting what one would expect when assessing a technology using a large amount of metals and other resources, the corresponding impact categories, such as metal depletion, are not among the highest categories used. Another critical impact associated with wind turbines is land use. Not only does their installation lead to land transformation, but along the supply chain, e.g., raw material extraction, it is linked to changes in land use. Contrary to those expectations, impact categories on land use, such as urban and agricultural land occupation and

natural land transformation, are amongst the least frequently evaluated impact categories. Especially when assessing a technology that is supposed to help reduce CC but is intense in raw materials and land use, those impact categories should be evaluated alongside CC to avoid shifting burdens from one category to another.

Figure 8: Frequency of reported impact categories of reviewed studies.

3.3 End-of-life treatment

The three “R” approaches (reduce, reuse and recycle) are a common practice to make products or services more sustainable. Applying the first “R” to wind turbines could be interpreted to, for example, reduce the waste of particular components that require treatment. Reusing is found to be practised today as the turbines can, under certain circumstances, be re-powered and get a second life. As a last option, the third “R” stands for recycling: if reduction and reuse strategies are not applicable, the turbines should be recycled to recover valuable materials.

When asking the interviewees about their EoL strategy for wind turbines, all stated that the first step is always to re-power existing installations. Some interviewees highlighted that the decision to re-power wind turbines is a complex problem involving different aspects, such as undertaken maintenance, existing permits, etc. In many cases, the wind turbines have not reached their EoL because they are not operational anymore. Instead, it’s a legal problem as the existing permits cannot be extended or renewed.

In case functional wind turbines do not have a permit anymore, they are transported to another location and reinstalled. Suppose the wind turbine is re-powered at the exact location; the primary goal is to increase the initial installation's capacity. From an LCA perspective, this means that some materials or subcomponents would have an extended lifetime, and thus, their environmental impact per generated kWh would be reduced. Moreover, with its focus on the entire life cycle of wind turbines, LCA offers a sound methodology to evaluate the environmental impacts of different EoL strategies. Depending on the selected impact assessment method, the difference in EoL treatment becomes visible. For example, while CC impacts per kWh of different EoL strategies for wind turbines might be small, increasing the recycling rate of metals when assessing mineral and metal resources might become very important. Thus, when investigating in different EoL strategies for wind turbines, it is important to consider not only CC, but also other impact assessment categories.

When looking at the EoL market, interviewees reported individual treatment solutions per installation on small scales based on different recycling technologies. The reason for those small and individual recycling solutions is primarily due to the absence of a sufficient waste stream. One interviewee, in particular, pointed towards a delay in those waste streams: Even though wind turbines are considered a relatively young technology, the first installations should have already reached their EoL by now. Instead, the components are used for different purposes, delaying their arrival at recycling facilities. However, it was also pointed out that the limited growth of the small recyclers is expected to be overcome with more and more wind turbines entering their EoL stage by 2030. Thus, larger recycling companies with more mature recycling processes for wind turbines can be expected.

Furthermore, it was mentioned that currently, most decommissioned components end up mainly in landfills. Alternative, some demonstration project can be for utilized for sound insulation along highways or similar. It is expected that in 10 years, a higher degree of recycling, meaning a better separation of materials, will be possible, thus allowing a higher degree of material circularity.

Recycling needs to be differentiated between the different materials: metals can be theoretically fully recovered (source). Also, the permanent magnets used in the generator can be reused after treatment. Those magnets are of interest as they contain rare earth metals, with underlying critical raw materials a recycling target. For other materials, such as polymers, the EoL

treatment becomes less straightforward. In particular, material components, such as those used in wind turbine blades, become particularly difficult to recover. The first challenge is knowing the share and type of materials used in the blades, which varies from turbine to turbine. Therefore, current research efforts are focused on publishing a wind turbine blades passport to know which materials are involved. As wind turbines are composed of several materials, no single recycling technology exists. Still, the interviewees stated that the future of wind turbine recycling technology will likely combine chemical, mechanical and thermal recycling. A still unsolved problem remains the treatment of the wind turbine blades.

Instead of grinding the blades and using the granulate, e.g. for low-value additives or using the residuals after thermal treatment in the foundation, which is found to be the current practice for EoL of the blades, the blades could, in the future, undergo chemical treatment. A solvent separates the epoxy resins from the glass fibres in this process. Unfortunately, the currently used solvent breaks down the glass fibres, making them unusable for further application. One potential solution could be to change the stoichiometric composition of the epoxy resins, so they become easier to break down and thus separate from the glass fibres. However, these modified epoxy resins are still under investigation, and the time to market such a changed technology is long. Some interviewees stated that chemical recycling of wind turbine blades could reach market maturity in 30 to 35 years. Thus, the exact treatment option of the blades remains open and is an object for further research. Furthermore, economic benefits of recycling composite materials used in the turbines are low due to cheap purchase prices of primary materials.

As a result of higher waste streams of wind turbines reaching their EoL, the recycling value chain will be better organized and more mature. At the same time, solvents used in the chemical recycling of wind turbine blades are expected to become cheaper, according to the interviewees. A potential EoL treatment of wind turbines is visualized in Figure 9, representing a combination of the inputs from the interviewees and [23].

Figure 9: Potential end-of-life treatment of wind turbines from 2030 onwards (source: [23] and interviews).

Besides findings related to EoL treatment of wind turbines, another point is raised in an interview. Due to material improvements, future wind turbine components are expected to have an increased lifetime between roughly 29 to 40 years. The average theoretical lifetime of wind turbines in the analyzed studies is 23 years, with six studies assuming a lifetime of 30 years, five studies calculated 25 years, while the majority (22 studies) report a lifetime of 20 years. Instead, practical lifetime of wind turbines can be much shorter, e.g. around 18 to 19 years due to repowering plans [16].

3.4 Foundations

While the foundation of onshore wind turbines is straightforward to dimension, offshore foundations are more complex. Currently, a range of

offshore foundation technologies are available: Monopile foundation, tripod foundation, jacket foundation, gravity foundation and floating foundation [24]. Floating foundations can be further distinguished into barge platforms, spar-buoy platforms, and semi-submersible and tension-leg platforms [21]. According to the interviewees, the selection of the foundation depends on the sea depth and the natural condition of the seabed where the wind turbines are to be installed: Monopile installations might be a feasible solution for wind turbines in shallow water areas, and a soft seabed, e.g. mainly based on sand like in the coast in front of the Netherlands. Unlike the Netherlands, a monopile foundation might not be feasible in areas of deep-water depths or with tough seabed ground, e.g. based on hard rock like in the Norwegian Sea. Similar observations are found in the literature [25] (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Different offshore foundations according to water depths [25].

Furthermore, one interviewee stated that jacket foundations are not used anymore without providing further information. Potential reasons, however, could be, for example, higher material needs, more complex transportation, or the mooring on the seabed. This trend is also visible in the analyzed literature: Four LCA studies of offshore wind turbines are conducted for floating foundations. In comparison, three studies investigate installations with a monopile foundation.

3.5 Existing LCA models for wind turbines

Wind turbines' environmental impacts depend in two ways on their location. First, different wind speeds at other locations result in different electricity yields, which are used to present the environmental impacts of wind energy per kWh. Second, different locations of the wind turbines require other transportation activities during installation, maintenance and EoL treatment. Additionally, the different locations require an extra length of power supply. Therefore, various research efforts were dedicated to visualizing the location-specific environmental impacts of wind energy. Those research efforts are presented in this chapter, together with their limitations.

3.5.1 EnerGE

One model was built more than ten years ago by MINES PARIS and is described in more detail in Blanch et al. (2012) [26]. The graphical user interface (GUI) allows us to evaluate four impact categories of offshore wind farms: CC, human health, ecosystem and resources. The farms are composed of 30, 40 or 50 wind turbines, and their impacts are located in the North Sea and between islands north of France and Norway (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: EnerGE GUI to present environmental impacts of offshore installations [26].

In its background, a geo-dependent LCA model is developed to consider distances from shore to the wind farm to calculate parameters such as the length of cables, the transportation distance, and the choice of foundation. The same research institute published a more recent LCA study, including primary data for an offshore wind farm in the North of France [27]. Unfortunately, due to data protection, no LCI data has been published. Limitations of this EnerGE web interface are the scope, e.g., it is focused only

on offshore installation. It neglects onshore installation, it only presents impacts for a specific part of northern Europe, and the fleet size is not adjustable, neither in numbers nor in rated power.

3.5.2 LCA_Wind_DK

More recently, the GUI “LCA_WIND_DK” has been developed based on the publications by Bessau et al. (2019) and Sacchi et al. (2019) [15], [16] to assess the CC of the Danish wind fleet and the energy return on invest based on fossil and renewable primary energy demand. Specifically, the assessment is built based on Danish wind turbine registry data and site-specific electricity production (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: LCA_WIND_DK GUI to present CC of Denmark's current and future wind turbine fleet [15], [16].

In the model's background, scaling models are developed to assess wind turbines, which are not included in the ecoinvent database. Compared to EnerGE, the LCA_WIND_DK model estimates actual onshore and offshore installations. However, it only looks at the Danish wind turbine fleet, assumes fixed transportation distances, and only monopiles as the foundation. Additionally, the assessment presents CC until 2030 and adjusts the electricity mix and the share of secondary steel. Changes of other background databases, such as efficiency improvements in the energy, steel and transport sectors remain subject to further research.

3.5.3 Windisch

Due to the lack of new capacities of single wind turbines in commercial databases, the need for publicly available LCI data on different wind turbines is more relevant than ever. Thus, the WIND_LCA_DK model described in Section 3.5.2 is built into a Python package to make LCI data of varying wind turbines. Once calculated, the LCI data is stored in a multi-dimensional array, allowing easy access and further processing (see Figure 13). Mass data can then be called for specific sizes and be further used, e.g. as in Figure 13.


```

Coordinates:
  size          (size)          <U6 '1000kW' '100kW' ... '8000kW'
array(['1000kW', '100kW', '3000kW', '500kW', '8000kW'], dtype='<U6')
  application   (application)    <U8 'offshore' 'onshore'
array(['offshore', 'onshore'], dtype='<U8')
  parameter     (parameter)    <U36 'access road' ... 'turbines per ...'
array(['access road', 'assembly electricity', 'cable mass', 'concrete density',
'concrete in foundation mass', 'distance to coastline', 'distance to assembly plant',
'distance to transformer', 'electronics mass', 'energy for cable lay-up', 'foundation mass',
'foundation transport to site', 'grout volume', 'hub height',
'installation energy', 'installation transport, by ship',
'installation transport, by truck', 'lifetime', 'maintenance transport',
'nacelle mass', 'nacelle transport to site',
'offshore farm cable cross-section', 'onshore farm cable cross-section',
'pile height', 'pile mass', 'rated power',
'reinforcing steel in foundation mass', 'rotor diameter', 'rotor mass',
'rotor transport to site', 'scour volume', 'sea depth',
'share foundation transport by rail',
'share foundation transport by sea',
'share foundation transport by truck',
'share maintenance transport by rail',
'share maintenance transport by sea', 'share nacelle transport by rail',
'share nacelle transport by sea', 'share nacelle transport by truck',
'share rotor transport by rail', 'share rotor transport by sea',
'share rotor transport by truck', 'share tower transport by rail',
'share tower transport by sea', 'share tower transport by truck',
'total mass', 'tower diameter', 'tower height', 'tower mass',
'tower transport to site', 'transition length', 'transition mass',
'transport for maintenance per year', 'transport to assembly',
'transport to waste facility', 'turbines per farm'], dtype='<U36')
  year          (year)          int32 2000 2010 2020 2030 2040 2050
array([2000, 2010, 2020, 2030, 2040, 2050])
  value         (value)          int32 0
array([0])
Indexes:
  size          PandasIndex
  application   PandasIndex
  parameter     PandasIndex
  year          PandasIndex
  value         PandasIndex
Attributes: (0)

```

Figure 13: Xarray of the windisch Python package [28].

For example, the mass of the different components of an 8 MW wind turbine is presented in Figure 14. Other information besides mass data is included in

this array, such as transport from and to the installation side share of materials, e.g., for the foundation. The package is still under development.

Figure 14: LCI data of an 8 MW offshore wind turbine obtained from windisch [28].

3.6 Outlook

The first step is to extend the windisch python package in three directions: first, a floating foundation model for offshore installations will be included. The offshore foundation will be selected depending on the sea depths and the rated power. In low water depths, a monopile foundation will be considered, and in areas with deep sea depths, floating foundations will be chosen, e.g., a rated power greater than 5 MW and a sea depth deeper than 50 meters (Figure 10). Second, the transportation distance of offshore wind turbines will be customized to the actual coordinates of the turbines. To the same extent, the length of the power cables will be customized according to the exact distance from shore to coast. Those two modifications require one main input: when specifying the turbine, the user must also provide the wind turbine coordinates. Given those coordinates, the model will calculate the distance of the installations from shore.

Once those changes are implemented in windisch, the material correlations presented in section 3.1 are used to calculate the environmental impact of different installations. The calculation of environmental impacts is divided into two parts: first, the existing EU wind fleet will be assessed based on data from wind turbine farms obtained from the windpower database. Second,

windisch will be modified for the WIMBY tool based on data from the installations provided by the project partners, such as rated power, annual electricity yield, etc.

The last part of the further developments will focus on the impact categories. First, results will be obtained using prospective LCI databases. Furthermore, different impacts apart from CC will be considered and, if possible, obtained from the project partners, such as land use changes, biodiversity, etc.

3.7 Discussion

According to the proposal, a workshop to collect primary data should have been organized. This approach was neglected because manufacturers data normally are classified as strictly confidential and underly a data protection clause. Instead, the literature review was extended to obtain correlations from published LCA. One main limitation is the number of studies included. An increased number of data would result in more precise correlation models. To determine the correlation between material masses and the components, linear regression models are used for all data points regardless of the fit of the regression model type, and the scope of the review is limited to materials used in the turbines, neglecting transportation, and energy requirements and other components and life cycle stages such as maintenance or EoL. Moreover, certain correlations need thorough evaluation, such as determining whether they arise from the data included in this review or if they result from causality. As the sample size of the included literature is limited, the absence of certain materials in particular wind turbine sizes could also be linked to the fact, that not enough or the right studies are included. One example is the absence of HDPE in nacelles at wind turbines larger than 5 MW. Additionally, the integration of the identified correlations remains open for the following year. Suppose those determined data about material correlations are deemed not helpful. In this case, a similar approach to that for LCA_WIND_DK will be followed based on published LCI data of wind turbines with rated power larger than 4.5 MW. A similar limitation concerns the conducted interviews: an increased sample would have helped to validate and further explore the perspective of future EoL treatment of wind turbines. Even though the number of samples could have been increased further to explore the future EoL treatment of wind turbines, it remains questionable to what extent this is currently possible,

given that the uncertainty linked to EoL treatment technology, particularly the blades, is still very high.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable is the first part of the WP2.4 Life Cycle Assessment of the WIMBY project. It presents a state-of-the-art literature review of studies about the environmental impacts of wind turbines. For this reason, relevant literature is identified from Elsevier's ScienceDirect given the search string "wind, life cycle thinking, sustainability, life cycle assessment and life cycle". After further qualitative filtering, the LCI data studies are collected and analysed. The objective is to identify correlations between masses of materials and rated power. Therefore, data is further harmonized, and a linear regression model is applied afterwards. Besides the literature review, semi-structured interviews were conducted to understand better the current and future potential of EoL treatment of wind turbines and the latest trends in offshore wind turbine foundations. Thus, a guideline is developed, and five semi-structured interviews are conducted.

Initially, 1,194 papers were identified in the literature review, which resulted in 101 studies after applying further filtering criteria. Of those, 30 papers are reviewed, of which 12 are excluded due to missing published LCI data. Material mass correlations with the rated power are presented for the foundations, the tower, the nacelle and the rotor. Overall, it is observed that more than 50% of the analysed studies are commissioned for onshore installations. On the contrary, wind turbines with a rated power per turbine greater or equal to 3 MW are mainly operated offshore. Depending on the component, more or less strong correlations are identified.

To conclude the literature study, the CC impacts of the studies are analysed. No clear advantages of offshore or onshore turbines are observed, and their average CC impact is 16.1 and 16.7 gCO₂eq/kWh, not remarkably divergent. Moreover, besides CC, the most applied impact categories of those reviewed studies are found to be ozone depletion and terrestrial acidification.

Concerning the EoL treatment of the wind turbines, the main challenge currently is the use of composite materials, such as glass-fibre reinforced plastic. Current research investigates facilitating the separation process by using different stoichiometric compositions of the resins and advancing the solvents. Another economic challenge is the absence of the treatment value chain, the cheap purchase prices of primary glass-fibre reinforced plastic and the postponed waste stream of wind turbines reaching their EoL.

Concerning the foundations, specialists indicated that the type of foundation depends on the sea depths and the seabed conditions. To conclude, three GUI are presented, visualizing CC impacts and LCI data of wind turbines.

The following steps to calculate the environmental impacts of wind turbines for WIMBY will be to use the correlation determined in this report combined with a Python package called *windisch*. Furthermore, different impacts besides CC evaluated within the WIMBY project will be included. Besides, methodological advancements will be elaborated to develop regionalized characterization factors. In the last step, a consequential LCA will be conducted to evaluate the environmental impacts of introducing more wind energy in the European energy systems with inputs from WP4.

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	Authors	Function al unit	System boundar ies	Publish ed LCI	Source of LCI	Operati ng years	Start of operati on	Country	Turbin e type	Foundatio n type	Energy model	Total installe d capacit y	Rated capac ity per turbin e
1	[14]	delivery of 1 GWh of electricity produced by the offshore floating wind farm to the onshore national grid	cradle-2-grave	Yes	Gaertner et al, 2020; Allen et al., 2020 and others	30	n.a.	Italy	Offshore	Floating (Tension-leg-platform)	Literature data	2,800,000	14,700
2	[20]	1 MWh of electricity	cradle-2-grave	yes	Basosi et al. 2020	30	2011	Italy	Onshore	n.a.	Literature data	18,000	2,000
3	[21]	2.5 MW directly driven permanent magnet	cradle-2-grave	no	eFootprint	20	n.a.	China	Onshore	n.a.	Survey data	2,500	2,500

		wind turbine											
4	[22]	1 kWh of electricity produced to the grid	cradle-2-grave	yes	Various literature resources	25	n.a.	China	Offshore	floating	Literature (smart windpower)	670	6,700
5	[23]	1 kWh power generated	cradle-2-grave	yes	China Three Gorges Corporation and GaBi	25	n.a.	China	Offshore	n.a.	Literature data	77,400,000	5,463
6	[12]	1 kWh of electricity from WPSS delivered to the grid	cradle-2-grave	yes	NREL, DTU and IEA	20, 25, 30	n.a.	China (Guangdong Province)	0	monopile	Calculated	5,000	5,000
7	[24]	1 kWh of electricity from the wind farm	cradle-2-grave	yes	Vestas & literature	20	n.a.	India (Karnataka)	Onshore	n.a.	Literature	56,100	1,650
8	[25]	1 kWh produced	cradle-2-grave	yes	Nordex	25	2014	Turkey	Onshore	n.a.	Nordex, primary data	47,500	2,500

		electricity											
9	[26]	1 year of operation of a 6 MW offshore floating wind turbine	cradle-2-grave	yes	Technical drawings and literature	20	n.a.	Mediterranean sea	Offshore	raft-buoy and spar-buoy foundation	Own calculations	6,000	6,000
10	[27]	1 MWh of electricity generated from a wind farm	cradle-2-grave	yes	Vestas report	20	2008	India (Karnataka)	Onshore	n.a.	Literature and calculations	16,500	1,650
11	[6]	1 kWh net of electricity produced from the wind farm and delivered	cradle-2-grave	yes	NREL	25	n.a.	Scotland	Offshore	monopiles (spar) and floating (semi-submersible)	Own calculations	15,500	6,000

		d to the grid											
1 2	[5]	1 kWh of electricity by the OWF, based on its lifetime generation	cradle-2-grave	yes	Vestas and others	20	2015	United Kingdom	Offshore	monopiles	n.a.	4,020,100	2,000
1 3	[28]	kWh	cradle-2-grave	yes	Vestas 80V	20	n.a.	n.a.	Offshore	barge	n.a.	2,000	2,000
1 4	[29]	kWh	cradle-2-grave	yes	n.a.	20	n.a.	Inner Mongolia	Onshore	n.a.	Literature	49,500	1,500
1 5	[30]	1 kWh of electricity delivered to the grid	cradle-2-grave	yes	Vestas V82-1.65 MW	20	n.a.	Colombia (Guajira)	Onshore	n.a.	n.a.	19,500	1,650
1 6	[31]	Generation of 1 kWh of average electricity from all three wind	cradle-2-grave	yes	GW77/1500	20	2015-2017	Ethiopia	Onshore	n.a.	Primary data	51,000,000	1,500

		farms connect ed to the national grid system											
17	[13]	structure of a wind tower, with a height of 185 m, designed for a service life of 20 years and supporting a wind turbine of 5.0 MW.	cradle-2-grave	yes	NREL 5 MW wind turbine	20	n.a.	Portugal	Onshore	6-Legged tower	Literature	5,000	5,000
18	[32]	1 kWh of electricity	cradle-2-grave	yes	Vestas, Enercon GmbH,	20	n.a.	Germany (Lower Saxony)	Onshore	n.a.	Own calculations	3,000	3,000

		delivered to the grid			Siemens AG								
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Table 1: Overview of included studies.

	Authors	Reason for exclusion
1	[10]	No LCI disclosed
2	[15]	Data will be made upon request
3	[11]	No LCA was conducted, nor mass balances nor sufficient material specifications
4	[33]	No detailed LCI are included due to an NDA
5	[34]	No LCI included
6	[35]	Materials aggregated per turbine
7	[36]	No LCI included
8	[37]	No LCI was used; there was a correlation between GHG and rated power, hub height, etc.
9	[38]	LCI is aggregated for entire wind turbines
10	[39]	Incomplete LCI (only materials in the manufacturing stage are reported)
11	[18]	LCI is aggregated
12	[40]	No LCI included, not a LCA study

Table 2: Overview of excluded studies.

ANNEX

Guideline semi-structured interview WIMBY (job creation and end-of-life strategies)

Methodology: Duration of the interview will be determined by interviewee.
(at least 30 min, max 1 hour)

Interviewed organizations (to be determined)

Organization related to lifecycle stages	number
Planning/development	A
Manufacturing	B
Development	C
Operation & maintenance	D
Decommissioning	E
Other	F

Key topics:

- Organization of interviewee
- Role of interviewee in organization
- Organizations relation to lifecycle stage of wind energy deployment (job sectors)
- Organizations involvement in wind energy deployment
- Jobs (quantities/duration(permanent or temporary)/location)
- Influence of project scale on jobs
- Difference between onshore and offshore regarding jobs
- Different foundation types and related bill of materials
- End-of-Life strategies

Guideline:

- At the start of the interview, we ask for a personal introduction, in the remaining of the interview, we are interested in the organizational involvement in wind energy deployment.

General introduction

(5 min)

- Introduction of the interviewer
- Introduction to the Master thesis and the research of Dominik
- Job creation questions for the Master thesis, and EoL questions for research of Dominik
- Data protection declaration
- Request for audio recording
- Use of citations for reporting

1. Warm-Up

(5 min)

Aim: introduction of the interviewee and organization

- Professional background, career
- Current areas of responsibilities
- Organization (type/business/size/years of experience)

2. Involvement in wind energy deployment

(10–15 min)

Aim: identify organizational involvement in the wind energy deployment

1. Lifecycle stages

Regarding the different lifecycle stages of wind turbines (planning/development, manufacturing, construction, operation and maintenance, and decommissioning), in which of these lifecycle stages is your organization involved?

2. Wind energy capacity it contributes to periodically/annually? (number of projects/turbines, scale of turbines, project scale)

*How many wind energy projects are you involved in per period/annually?
And what is the size of these projects in terms of number of projects,
number of turbines, total installed capacity?*

** if interviewee cannot answer this question ask for size, number of turbines etc of a typical wind project.*

3. Duration of the involvement in a wind energy project?

What is the duration of your organizations involvement in a wind energy project?

** if interviewee cannot answer this question ask for general involvement duration for similar organizations to a typical wind project*

3. Jobs (type/duration/temporal nature/location) (5-10 min)

Aim: determine amount of jobs related to the organizations activity

1. Number of employees/ jobs

How many employees (including outsources jobs) are required for your organizations involvement in a wind project (in terms of jobs/project or jobs/turbine or jobs/MW)?

2. Temporary nature of the jobs

What is the temporal nature of the jobs related to wind energy projects in your organization?

If temporary jobs are present: What share of total jobs is temporary and what is the duration of these temporary jobs?

3. Local/national/international job creation

Where are the jobs located that your organization created for wind energy projects?

4. Onshore vs Offshore, scale influences (5-10 min)

Aim: Create insights in influence and difference on job creation between onshore and offshore wind deployment and different sized wind parks

1. Difference onshore and offshore jobs

How do onshore and offshore wind jobs differ from each other in terms of employees required and job duration?

2. Influence of wind project scale on jobs

How does project scale (installed capacity, number of turbines) influence the amount of employees required and the job duration?

5. Data on foundation and end of Life treatment (10-15 min)

Aim: create insights in different offshore wind turbine foundations and related bills of materials.

1. Which different foundation options for offshore wind turbines do you know? Do you know/have primary data about bill of materials for those different foundation types that you can share? If you do not have any data by yourself, do you have some contacts that can help with this question?

Aim: provide overview of state-of-the-art end-of-life of wind turbines.

2. Which end-of-life option do you foresee to be the state-of-the-art treatment option per wind turbine component in Europe by 2030/2050? How do you expect a future end-of-life treatment industry for used wind turbines to look like by 2030/2050? Can you

share any data/reports/further information about end-of-life treatment?

6. Wrap-Up – Final Self-Reflection

(5 min)

Aim: invite interviewee to address to topics that we have not yet touched upon and ask for additional contacts and/or recommendations.

Which other organizations can be interested in participating in this interview?

Thank you for your time and the information provided. Are there any topics/issues regarding wind energy deployment and jobs that you would like to discuss with us?

Thank you for your time and for the interview!

